

Viscoelastic Properties of highly filled Cabroxy-terminated Polybutadiene Composites

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The objectives of this work were to investigate the mechanical and viscoelastic behaviour of some filled rubbers in order to throw light on the static and dynamic behaviour of these polymers when used as propellant binders. Since the polymers under considerations were to be used as binders, the filler content of the filled samples exceeded significantly the conventional magnitude of the binder¹.

Fillers used in rocket propellants are ammonium perchlorate and aluminium powder. However, in order to avoid explosion hazards, the samples in the investigations were dummy ones, containing potassium chloride, instead of ammonium perchlorate. To understand the dependence of viscoelastic properties on filler content and on the type of the filler used, more formulations (systems) comprising of barium chloride, barium fluoride and barium chloride anhydrous, have also been studied².

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the magnitudes of mechanical loss factor ($\tan \delta$) when it reaches the maximum ($\tan \delta_{\max}$) value, the temperature at which the maximum occurs, and the concentration of the filler samples. The concentration of aluminium powder (20 phr) was kept constant with respect to the mass of the resin, in order to understand the effect of KCl on the properties of the composites. It can be seen from Figs. 1 and 2 that during the pre- and post-glass transition temperature region, the magnitude of loss factor shows little influence of filler concentration, while over the transition region (when

Fig. 1. $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature; curing time = 72 h.

$\tan \delta$ passes through the maximum), the said influence is prominent. Generally, the $\tan \delta_{\max}$ values get suppressed as the filler concentration increases³. This effect is observed irrespective of curing time (72 h and 120 h, Figs. 1 and 2).

For a lower curing time (72 h; Fig. 1), there is a wider variation in the magnitudes of the temperature corresponding to $\tan \delta_{\max}$. This may be due to a lower degree of averaging of the thermal environment (since the time for curing is shorter) to which the filled formulations were subjected⁴.

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TABLE 1—FORMULATION DETAILS TEMPERATURE AT WHICH MAXIMUM LOSS FACTOR OCCURRED

Formulation no.	Contents (Phr)		Curing time h	tan δ_{max} $\times 10^2$	Temp. at tan δ_{max} °C
	KCl	Al			
1	—	20	72	177	-47
2	40	20	72	141	-44
3	75	20	72	168	-33
4	120	20	72	158	-37
5	135	20	72	138	-42
6	30	20	120	151	-48
7	50	20	120	174	-44
8	60	20	120	167	-41
9	90	20	120	129	-39
10	135	20	120	119	-42

It is worthwhile to compare the storage modulus (E') of various samples at a common temperature. The fall in the magnitude of E' at -60° can be anticipated at the higher concentration range of the filler used, when the filler particles are likely to largely remain isolated (Fig. 3). The particles would aggregated and would get isolated from the matrix as proposed by Takayanagi⁵. At -30° however, E' values prominently increases with filler content (Fig. 4). This can be explained on the basis of wettability of polymer. Wettability tends to increase due to

Fig. 2. tan δ as a function of temperature; curing time = 120 h.

Fig. 3. Storage modulus as a function of % of filler in the composite at -60° .

relaxation of polymeric chains above T_g , as the viscous behaviour predominates elastic behaviour.

Conclusions : (i) The influence of filler on glass transition temperature in the pre-transition and post-transition temperature range, is very feeble while that during the transition temperature range is

Fig. 4. Storage modulus as a function of % of filler in the composite at -30° .

profound. (ii) Time of cure does not have much effect on mechanical loss factor $\tan \delta$, after the curing process is over. (iii) During the temperature range from -30° to -60° , the magnitudes of storage modulus exhibit a tremendous increase due to freezing of the segmental motion of the polymer chains. At -30° , storage modulus increases with % of KCl (filler), while at -60° , there is initial increase in the magnitude of storage modulus followed by a slight decline. This is possibly due to isolation of filler particles (dewetting) from the composites. This is in conformity with the theory proposed by Takayanagi⁵.

Experimental

Carboxy-terminated polybutadiene (CTPB), potassium chloride, aluminium powder and curing agents were obtained from Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Trivandrum.

Formulation and specimen preparation : Binder, fillers and curing agents were thoroughly mixed and the mix was poured on to a clean, flat glass plate coated with a non-sticky silicon emulsion. This plate was kept in a precisely controlled oven at $90 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The mix were cured for 72 and 120 h. Rectangular specimens were obtained by cutting with a punch.

Dynamic mechanical analysis : It was carried out on a Du Pont DMA 981 analyser from -120° under a heating rate of $5^\circ/\text{min}$ to 10° . DMA module

was coupled to a Du Pont 982 thermal analyser. Regulated nitrogen gas flow ($2.5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) was generated by pressurising liquid nitrogen in a Dewar flask to purge the system at a constant pressure.

DMA operates on the compound resonance principle, in which the sample is allowed to vibrate freely (at its resonant frequency) and vibrational amplitude is maintained constant by supplying adequate force to the sample by an electronic feed-back mechanism. The resonant frequency is related to sample storage modulus (E') while the force required to maintain the amplitude constant is a measure of loss modulus (E'')⁶.

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